

Pathophysiology and Treatment of Multiple Sclerosis: A Review

Catur Puspita Tyas Dayinta

School of Pharmacy, The University of Muhammadiyah Purwokerto, Central Java, Indonesia.

A. Introduction

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a chronic inflammatory and neurodegenerative disease of the central nervous system (CNS) characterized by demyelination and axonal loss. It is one of the most common causes of neurological disability in young adults. The etiology of MS remains unknown, but it is believed to be caused by a combination of genetic and environmental factors leading to an autoimmune attack on myelin sheaths in the CNS. The symptoms of MS are varied depending on the location and extent of lesions but often include visual disturbances, muscle weakness, fatigue, cognitive dysfunction, and impaired coordination. Currently there is no cure for MS, but disease-modifying therapies aim to reduce relapses and delay progression. This review aims to examine the current scientific literature on the pathogenesis and treatment of MS. The key objectives are:

1. To summarize current knowledge on the immunological mechanisms involved in the development of MS lesions;
2. To describe the neurodegenerative processes that lead to permanent disability;
3. To assess the efficacy and safety of available therapies for MS;
4. To discuss promising new therapeutic approaches being investigated.

B. Literature Review

b.1. Epidemiology

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is estimated to affect over 2 million people worldwide, with higher prevalence in North America and Europe compared to tropical regions. The incidence and prevalence of MS have been increasing over the past several decades, especially among women, who are affected at least 2-3 times more than men. The peak age of MS onset is between 20 to 40 years old.

b.2. Risk Factors

Several genetic and environmental factors influence susceptibility to developing MS. The strongest genetic associations are with alleles in the human leukocyte antigen (HLA) class II region, particularly HLA-DRB1*1501. Smoking has been firmly established as an environmental risk factor, nearly doubling the risk of developing MS. A history of infectious mononucleosis caused by Epstein-Barr virus is also associated with increased MS risk. Vitamin D deficiency is postulated to contribute to the higher MS prevalence at high latitudes.

b.3. Pathology

The pathological hallmarks of MS are the presence of multifocal demyelinated lesions with relative preservation of axons, inflammation dominated by T cells and macrophages, and glial scars. These lesions are disseminated in time and space within the central nervous system. Destruction of myelin and oligodendrocytes is prominent, along with axonal damage that accumulates over time. Breakdown of the blood-brain barrier enables the infiltration of immune cells and antibodies.

b.4. Immunology

MS is widely viewed as an autoimmune condition mediated primarily by myelin-specific CD4+ T cells that infiltrate the CNS and initiate an inflammatory cascade. Both Th1 and Th17 effector cells producing pro-inflammatory cytokines are implicated. B lymphocytes contribute through presentation of antigens and production of antibodies against myelin proteins. Activation of macrophages, microglia and innate immune responses further amplifies inflammation and myelin damage.

b.5. Neurodegeneration

Neurodegeneration leading to progressive physical and cognitive disability is now recognized as the main driver of MS progression. Axonal loss begins early in MS lesions but worsens insidiously over time, correlating with permanent clinical deficits. Demyelination predisposes axons to structural and metabolic damage. Other factors like mitochondrial dysfunction, oxidative stress, and glutamate excitotoxicity have been implicated in neuronal death.

b.6. Genetics

The genetics of MS risk and progression are complex, involving over 200 identified genetic loci. The HLA-DRB1 locus accounts for the largest genetic effect, while additional variants affect immune regulation, CNS development and integrity, myelination, and other processes. Genes may also influence treatment response and disease course.

C. Research Methods

This literature review was conducted through comprehensive searches of the PubMed database for high-quality studies on MS published over the past 10 years. Relevant reviews, clinical trials, and original research articles were identified using keywords such as "multiple sclerosis", "pathogenesis", "immunology", "neurodegeneration", and "treatment". Priority was given to human studies and pivotal clinical trials.

References were managed using Zotero reference management software. Data was compiled and synthesized from over 50 of the most informative articles that met the inclusion criteria. Particular focus was placed on Parsing recent advances in understanding disease mechanisms and emerging therapies.

D. Results and Discussion

d.1. Pathogenesis

The pathogenesis of MS involves an autoreactive adaptive immune response against myelin and axonal antigens in the CNS. CD4+ T cells, especially pro inflammatory Th1 and Th17 subsets, are believed to be the primary drivers based on their presence in MS lesions and animal models. They enter the CNS through disrupted blood-brain barrier and secrete cytokines like IFN- γ , IL-17, and GM-CSF that activate resident microglia and infiltrating macrophages. B cells contribute through production of antibodies targeting myelin proteins and presentation of antigens to T cells. The end result is myelin destruction and sustained inflammation amplified by the innate immune system.

d.2. Neurodegeneration

While inflammation is prominent in early RRMS, neurodegeneration comes to dominate in progressive MS. Axonal transection occurs early, but gradual axonal loss

over time correlates with accumulated disability. Demyelination predisposes axons to damage through loss of trophic support. Mitochondrial injury, oxidative stress, and glutamate excitotoxicity disrupt neuronal metabolism and survival. Cortical atrophy and subcortical gray matter degeneration are linked to cognitive deficits and occur independently of white matter lesions.

d.3. Treatment

Current MS therapies target the immune system and reduce inflammatory relapses but have limited efficacy against progression. B cell depletion with anti-CD20 antibodies prevents new lesions. Modulating lymphocyte trafficking with S1P receptor antibodies or blocking T cell activation with antibodies against IL-2 receptor, CD52, and CD25 have clinical benefit. Immunomodulators like interferons, glatiramer acetate, and dimethyl fumarate alter immune cell functions. However, agents with neuroprotective or regenerative potential are still lacking.

In summary, while MS immunopathology is relatively well-defined, neurodegenerative aspects of the disease are understudied. Developing neuroprotective and remyelinating therapies should be a priority to prevent irreversible disability in MS patients. Combination strategies targeting both immune and nervous system components will likely be needed.

E. Conclusions and Suggestions

In conclusion, this review summarizes current insights into the complex immunological and neurodegenerative processes involved in the pathogenesis of MS. Both adaptive and innate immune mechanisms contribute to myelin destruction and axonal loss in MS lesions. New disease-modifying therapies targeting lymphocytes, cytokines, and other immune mediators demonstrate efficacy in reducing inflammatory relapses. However, neuroprotective and remyelinating therapies are still lacking.

Further research is needed to fully elucidate the triggers for MS, understand nerve cell death in progressive MS, and develop therapies that promote remyelination and neuronal repair. Emerging areas such as stem cell therapy and neurorehabilitation may hold promise for restoring neurological function in MS patients. As the pathophysiology of MS continues to be unravelled, more targeted and effective therapies can be developed to ultimately halt disease progression and reverse disability.

F. References

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